

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF FLOW SEPERATION DELAY OVER AN AIRFOIL BY CONTINUOUS BLOWING

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Abstract— This article covers the flow separation over the airfoils is unavoidable due to the formation of large adverse pressure gradient. However, such flow separation has a great negative effect on the flow characteristics over the airfoil and significantly influence the aerodynamic performance of the airfoil. The idea of flow control over airfoils to improve the aerodynamic performance has attracted wide spread research interest in the area of aerodynamics and wind engineering. Current research proposes an active flow control method by utilizing perpendicular blowing over an airfoil to enhance the aerodynamic characteristics of the airfoil by effectively delaying the flow separation NACA 2415 airfoil were chosen for the study and the computational investigations were carried out at various angles of attack ranging from 0° to 35° at a mean free stream velocity corresponding to $Re=4.2 \times 10^5$. The effect of perpendicular blowing for different chordwise location. The chordwise blowing positions are varied at 30%, 50% and 80% of the chord and the jet velocity was 60m/s to the free stream velocity. Result of this study demonstrated that the modified model with blowing jet velocity of 120m/s at 30% of chord increases maximum coefficient of lift to 38% and the maximum L/D ratio to 6% compare to the baseline airfoil.

Keywords— flow separation, airfoil NACA 2415, flow control, Blowing

I.INTRODUCTION

Due to air traffic and increasing cost [15], flow control technologies are introduced to reduce fuel consumption and direct operating cost. Aim of the flow control [9] is to attain different engineering ideas. Airplane wing performance is not only affected by the runway length, climb [13] rate, approach speed, capacity of cargo and range but also decreased by the flow separation. Goals or ideas like formation of fluid layer like around wing surface of an aircraft or external surface of submarine. It is mainly depending on the aerodynamic design of the airfoil profile. The separation of the air flow over an airfoil is difficult to control. Controlling such layer laid way to alter transition delay, lift enhancement, heat transfer enhancement, turbulence augmentation, skin friction reduction.

A. Boundary layer separation

Air flow becomes detached from the surface of the airfoil and instead takes the forms of eddies and vortices. Result in pressure drag which is caused by pressure difference between the front and rear surfaces of the airfoil as it travels through the air. It also occurs when the portion of the boundary layer closed to the wall or leading-edge reverses in flow direction. Separation point is defined as point between forward and backward flow, where the shear stress is zero. Flow reversal is primarily caused by adverse pressure gradient.

B. Flow separation

All solid object travelling through the fluid or stationary object exposed through the moving fluid creates a boundary layer of fluid around them. Flow separation occurs when the boundary layer travels far enough against the adverse pressure gradient that the speed of the boundary layer relative to the object falls almost to zero. The fluid flow becomes detached from the surface of the object, and instead takes the forms of vortices. In aerodynamic flow separation often result in increased drag, mainly pressure drag, which is caused by the pressure difference between the front and the rear surface of the object as it travels through the fluids [11]-[16]. To avoid the increasing drag induced in the object research has gone in the design of aerodynamic surface which delays the flow separation and keep the flow attached to the object for as possible. In an airfoil the flow gets separates due to the curvature. The curved surface creates the vortices in the surface of the airfoil which resist the flow and separates it. Boundary layer separation is the detachment of the boundary layer from the surface into a broader wake. Boundary layer separation occurs when the portion of the boundary layer closes to the wall or leading-edge reverses in the flow direction the separation point is defined as the point between forward and backward flow, where the shear stress is zero. Flow control technique mainly classified into three, they are passive (no energy expenditure), active (involve energy) and hybrid flow control. These are mainly attempted to change the flow around the body, reduce wake, prevent separation, and mass transfer into the boundary layer. These methods are used to obtain desirable change in the flow pattern and the boundary layer.

C. Active Flow Control

The main aim is to alter the natural flow or to develop the desired flow path. It involves addition of auxiliary power to the flow, and that helps to delay the flow separation in an airfoil. It is divided into 2 categories, predetermined and interactive method. Active Flow Control methods are steady suction or blowing, unsteady suction or blowing, actuators, controllers and sensors.

D. Passive Flow Control

There is no auxiliary power and no loops are required to control the flow separation. The principle is to mixing high momentum fluid to areas of low momentum fluid. Passive Flow Control methods are to place the longitudinal grooves and rib lets over an airfoil surface, geometric shaping and use the vortex generator.

E. Hybrid Flow Control

To provide lift enhancement necessary for simple hinged flap high-lift system. Drag reduction also occur up to 3.3 counts due to elimination of fowler flap fairings.

Active control method yields better results in drag reduction than passive control method.

F. Different types of flow control techniques

It emerges from different methodology of boundary layer flow that the boundary conditions i.e., the distributions of outer velocities and the wall temperature or the wall heat flux.

As well as these natural ways of controlling the boundary layer through the usual boundary conditions, different method have also been developed to bring about certain types of behaviour in the boundary layer through artificial means.

Motion of the solid wall:

One optional method of avoiding separation would be to completely prevent the formation of boundary layer. Since, the boundary layer over its existence to the velocity differences the wall and the outer flow. Could be eliminated altogether by ensuring that the velocity difference removed. This can be achieved by moving the wall along with the flow. A moving wall can be most simply realized in the rotation of circular cylinder in a flow. The flow field is un symmetric. The inviscid outer flow corresponds to the cylinder flow with circulation. This flow produces a transverse flow known as magnetic effect.

Fig 1.1 The velocity profile near the separation point in the boundary layer at moving wall.

G. Slit suction

It was already in the first piece of work by L.Prandtl (1904) on boundary layer[1] that he artificially influenced the boundary layer in order to conform his fundamental ideal.

When suction is applied to one side through a narrow slit. The flow follows along the surface of the body where the suction is applied for considerable distance that preventing separation.

H. Tangential blowing and suction

Further ways to prevent the separation consist of supplying additional energy to the particular fluid flow. This can be done by blowing higher velocity fluid out from the suction inside body.

Fig 1.2 Blowing and Suction method

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study [1],[2] investigates the effects of blowing parameters on flow control for a NACA 0012 airfoil. Tangential and perpendicular blowing at the trailing edge were applied, varying jet widths (1.5-4% chord length) and amplitudes (0.1-0.5). Results show a 15% lift-drag ratio increase with higher tangential blowing amplitudes. Smaller amplitudes are more effective for perpendicular blowing. Under tangential blowing, a 17% lift-to-drag ratio increase is observed at an 18-degree angle of attack. Additionally, jet width variations impact performance, with a continuous increase in lift-to-drag ratio in tangential blowing and a quasi-linear decrease in perpendicular blowing. Optimal conditions involve tangential blowing with a 0.5 amplitude, 4% jet width, and an 18-degree angle of attack. These findings offer insights for optimizing aerodynamic surfaces using blowing techniques.

This study [3],[4],[5] explores the influence of jet width variations on blowing and suction flow control for a NACA 0012 airfoil, using RANS equations and Menter's turbulent model. Jet widths ranged from 1.5% to 4% of the chord length, with jet velocities at 0.3 and 0.5 of the free-stream velocity. Results indicate a continuous lift-to-drag ratio increase with wider blowing jet widths in tangential blowing, contrasting with a quasi-linear decrease in perpendicular blowing. Suction control enhances the lift-to-drag ratio, peaking at a 2.5% chord length jet width. At a Reynolds number of 5×10^5 and varying angles of attack, suction control with larger amplitudes significantly improves the lift-to-drag ratio and stall angle. Optimal jet widths for suction control at the airfoil's leading edge are identified as 2.5% to 3% of the chord length. These findings provide concise insights into effective jet width manipulation for enhanced aerodynamic performance.

This numerical investigation [8] focuses on tangential and perpendicular steady blowing at the trailing edge of a NACA 0012 airfoil for flow separation control. Optimal blowing jet placement is identified at 80 percent of the chord length from the leading edge. Increasing blowing amplitude has minimal impact on lift and drag coefficients. Tangential blowing leads to a gradual stall, while perpendicular blowing enhances the stall angle from 14 to 16 degrees. The most significant lift-to-drag ratio improvement occurs at a blowing amplitude of 0.5 and a blowing coefficient of 0.00875, demonstrating reduced back vortices at an 18-degree angle of attack.

This study [6],[7] compares conventional straight wings with tubercled wings, acknowledging the latter's superior performance in the pre-stall region despite increased flow complexity and susceptibility to separation. Numerical investigations were conducted on tubercled wings with surface blowing at different jet velocities and chordwise positions. Results demonstrate improved performance over the conventional tubercled wing, highlighting the efficacy of blowing at various chordwise positions with different velocity ratios. The study further explores the impact of blowing velocity ratio (R) and blowing location (L) on both baseline and modified tubercled wings at various angles of attack. Optimizing blowing parameters can significantly enhance the aerodynamic efficiency of tubercled wings.

III. COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

A. Introduction to CFD

Figure. 3.1. Process of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD)

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is the simulation of fluids engineering systems using modelling (mathematical physical problem formulation) and numerical methods (discretization methods, solvers, numerical parameters, and grid generations, etc.). The process is as figure 1. Firstly, we have a fluid problem. To solve this problem, we should know the

physical [16]-[21],[23] properties of fluid by using Fluid Mechanics. Then we can use mathematical equations to describe these physical properties [13]. This is Navier-Stokes Equation and it is the governing equation of CFD. As the Navier-Stokes Equation is analytical, human can understand it and solve them on a piece of paper. But if we want to solve this equation by computer, we have to translate it to the discretized form. The translators are numerical discretization methods, such as Finite Difference, Finite Element, Finite Volume methods. Consequently, we also need to divide our whole problem domain into many small parts because our discretization is based on them. Then, we can write programs to solve them. The typical languages are Fortran and C. Normally the programs are run on workstations or supercomputers. At the end, we can get our simulation results. We can compare and analyze the simulation results with experiments and the real problem. If the results are not sufficient to solve the problem, we have to repeat the process [16] until find satisfied solution. This is the process of CFD.

B. Significance of CFD

Fluid dynamics is studied through three methods: theoretical analysis, experiments, and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). CFD, being a relatively new method, offers numerous advantages over traditional experiments. Its widespread adoption in various industries, including aerospace, automotive, biomedicine, chemical processing, heat ventilation air conditioning, hydraulics, power generation, sports, and marine, underscores the broad applicability and efficiency of CFD in diverse fields.

C. Navier-Stokes Equation

The Navier-Stokes equations are analytical equations. Human can understand and solve them, but if we want to solve them by computer, we have to transfer them into discretized form. This process is discretization. The typical discretization methods are finite difference, finite element and finite volume methods. Here we introduce finite volume method. If we use finite difference and finite element approach to discretized Navier-Stokes equation, we have to manually control the conservation of mass, momentum and energy. But with finite volume method, we can easily find out that, if the Navier-Stokes equation is satisfied in every control volume, it will automatically be satisfied for the whole domain. In another words, if the conservation is satisfied in every control volume, it will be automatically satisfied in whole domain. That is the reason why finite volume is preferred in computational fluid dynamics.

D. The approach of Finite Volume Method

Integrate the general form of Navier-Stokes equation over a control volume and apply Gauss Theory

$$\int_V \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \Phi dV = \int_S \Phi \cdot n_i dS \quad (3.1)$$

We can get the integral form of Navier-Stokes equation

$$\int_V \frac{\partial(\rho\Phi)}{\partial t} dV + \int_S \left(\rho U_i \Phi - \Gamma \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial x_i} \right) \cdot n_i dS = \int_V q_\Phi dV \quad (3.2)$$

To approximate the volume integral, we can multiply the volume and the value at the center of the control volume. To approximate the mass and momentum of control volume P, we have

$$m = \int_{V_i} \rho dV \approx \rho_p V, \quad mu = \int_{V_i} \rho u_i dV \approx \rho_p u_p V \quad (3.3)$$

To approximate the surface integral, for example pressure force, we have

$$\oint_{S_i} P dS \approx \sum_k P_k S_k \quad k = n, s, e, w \quad (3.4)$$

Normally we store our variables at the center of control volume, so we need to interpolate them to get PK, which are located at the surface of control volume. Typically, we have two types of interpolations, one is upwind interpolation, and the other one is central interpolation.

1) Upward Interpolation:

$$U_e = \begin{cases} U_P & \text{if } (\vec{U} \cdot \vec{n})_e > 0 \\ U_E & \text{if } (\vec{U} \cdot \vec{n})_e < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

2) Central Interpolation:

$$U_e = U_E \lambda_e + U_P (1 - \lambda_e) \quad \lambda_e = \frac{x_e - x_P}{x_E - x_P} \quad (3.6)$$

3) Turbulent kinetic energy k :

$$\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \text{div}(\rho k \mathbf{U}) = \text{div} \left(\underbrace{-\overline{p' \mathbf{u}'}}_{(I)} + \underbrace{2\overline{\mu \mathbf{u}' e_{ij}'}}_{(II)} - \underbrace{\rho \frac{1}{2} \overline{u_i' u_j'}}_{(III)} \right) - \underbrace{2\overline{\mu e_{ij}' e_{ij}'}}_{(IV)} + \underbrace{(-\overline{\rho u_i' u_j' E_{ij}'})}_{(V)} \quad (3.7)$$

Here e_{ij}' is fluctuating component of rate of deformation tensor.

This equation can be read as:

(I) Rate of change of k , plus

(II) Transport of k by convection equals

(III) Transport of k by pressure, plus

(IV) Transport of k by viscous stresses, plus

(V) Transport of k by Reynolds stresses, minus

(VI) Rate of dissipation of k , plus

(VII) Turbulence production.

The equation for k contains additional turbulent fluctuation terms that are unknown. The following (simplified) model equation for k is commonly used. The Prandtl number σ_k connects the diffusivity of k to the eddy viscosity. Typically, a value of 1.0 is used.

4) Turbulent dissipation rate ε : However, the k equation mainly contains primed quantities, indicating that changes in k are mainly governed by turbulent interactions. Furthermore, term (VII) is equal in both equations. But it is actually negative in the K equation (destruction) and positive in the k equation: energy transfers from the mean flow to the turbulence. The viscous dissipation term (VI) in the k equation

$$-2\overline{\mu e_{ij}' e_{ij}'} \quad (3.10)$$

Describes the dissipation of k because of the work done by the smallest eddies against the viscous stresses. We can now define the rate of dissipation per unit mass ε as:

$$\varepsilon = 2\nu \overline{e_{ij}' e_{ij}'} \quad (3.10)$$

5) Model equation for ε : A model equation for ε is derived by multiplying the k equation by (ε/k) and introducing model constants. The following (simplified) model equation for ε is commonly used

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \varepsilon)}{\partial t} + \text{div}(\rho \varepsilon \mathbf{U}) = \text{div} \left[\frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \text{grad } \varepsilon \right] + C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} 2\overline{\mu_t E_{ij}' E_{ij}'} - C_{2\varepsilon} \rho \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} \quad (3.10)$$

The Prandtl number σ_ε connects the diffusivity of ε to the eddy viscosity. Typically, a value of 1.30 is used. Typically values for the model constants $C_{1\varepsilon}$ and $C_{2\varepsilon}$ of 1.44 and 1.92 are used.

E. DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF AN AIRFOIL

1) **GAMBIT (Modelling and Meshing)**: GAMBIT, standing for Geometry and Meshing Built-In Tool, is software designed for modelling test specimens and meshing them within the domain. It is predominantly favoured by aerodynamicists for analysis due to its straightforwardness, user-friendly interface, and operational flexibility. Its suitability for beginners is enhanced by features like the transcript box and description box, providing information on processes and commands. Notably, GAMBIT is the sole software offering undo and redo commands crucial for beginners. The software guides users through a systematic, step-by-step procedure for creating both the domain and the model.

F. MODELLING AND MESHING

Step 1: For this methodology we use *naca.exe* software to develop the required airfoil coordinates by selecting the airfoil series which 4, 5 or 6 digits with 30 points coordinates will create and it should be saved.

Step 2: After developing the required airfoil coordinates in *naca.exe* software. It should be opened in excel file for importing. The Z coordinates value which is zero at all point.

Step 3: Selecting the table and should be saved in the notepad. We can keep it to import the coordinates into gambit software.

Step 4: In ANSYS gambit 2.4 software select file option then import the vertex data which is saved in Note pad.

Fig 3.2 Vertex creation of airfoil in GAMBIT

Step 5: The coordinates of NACA 2415 airfoil is appeared in the display. The vertex should be turned into edge by create edges command. It creates the real or virtual edges. Number command is used to creating the edges subjected with vertex. It should be created by two edges such as upper and lower.

Fig 3.3 Converting vertex into edges

Step 6: Hereafter the edges are converted into face based on predefined primitives, facing help for smooth appearance of model by selecting the upper edges and lower edges.

Fig 3.4 converting edges into face

Step 7: Face command used to create a face based on predefined primitives we use rectangle option to create a domain with top-down ratio of 1:1 and front & back ratio of 1:4 respectively.

Step 8: We use subtract option which is in Boolean operations on faces to subtract the model from the domain area.

Step 9: Mesh command used to create and modified the meshing in mesh command the involving edges should be selected after that the mesh facing will be carried out to create the mesh element such as Quad, triangle or Quad/triangle. Triangle option should be used for easy assessment.

Fig 3.5 Meshing of the airfoil with domain

Step 10: Specify boundary types by initiate the name and type of the operational requirements.

Position	Boundary types
Inlet	Velocity inlet
Outlet	Pressure outlet
Sides	Symmetry
Model	Wall

TABLE I BOUNDARY CONDITIONS FOR BASELINE MODEL

Step 11: After creating the boundary conditions, specifying the continuum by using appropriate command. This command specifies continuum types such as fluid, solid or porous. We select fluid for our operation.

Name	Continuum type
Air	Fluid

TABLE II FLOW PROPERTIES

Step12: For creating part will be added, which is involvement for additional command we use straight line to different chord wise locations

modified models, the one more blower unit. There is no commands. Instead of nurbs create the blower spot on such as 0.3c, 0.5c, 0.8c.

Fig 3.6 Blower at 0.3 chord

Fig 3.7 Blower at 0.5 chord

Fig 3.8 Blower at 0.8 chord

Step 13: Likewise, baseline modelling, modified model should be converted into face from edges. Then domain will be created as similar to the baseline model. And then meshing is to be initialized as similar to the baseline model.

Step 14: As similar to the baseline model boundary condition for the modified model is applied in addition to that velocity inlet is set for the blower in modified model.

Step 15: Thus, the modelling and meshing is done on GAMBIT, further analysis is done on ANSYS FLUENT.

Name	Boundary Types
Inlet	Velocity inlet
Outlet	Pressure outlet
Sides	Symmetry
Model	Wall
Blower	Velocity inlet

TABLE III BOUNDARY CONDITIONS FOR MODIFIED MODEL

G. ANALYSIS

On completing the modelling and meshing, it is saved and exported as a mesh file for further analysis in ANSYS-FLUENT. Then open fluent and read the mesh file and the further conditions are given in a sequential order as shown in fig.3.9

Fig 3.9 Schematic representation of steps in FLUENT

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Initially, we tested the NACA 2415 airfoil at free stream velocity of 60 m/s at various angle of attack from 0 to 35° in the range of 5° for change in lift drag characteristics and the results was compared with change in lift and drag characteristics of the modified model manipulated by blower at different chordwise positions such as 30%, 50% and 80% of the chord at the free stream velocity of 60m/s and the blowing velocity of 60m/s.

A. Blowing at 30% of chord

1) *Lift characteristics*: The comparison of lift characteristic of the baseline and modified model with blower at 30 percent of total chord length is studied using graph plot between coefficient of lift vs angle of attack as shown in fig 4.1 and pressure contours as shown in fig 4.2, fig 4.3. In baseline model the maximum coefficient of lift is 1.1208114 which obtains at 15° AOA. Whereas, in modified model with blower at 30 percent of total chord length attains maximum coefficient of lift at 25° is 1.21783. In baseline model the stall angle takes place between 15° to 20°. But in the modified model the stall angle takes place between 25° to 30°. The effect of using blower in the modified model is to increase stall angle as well as increase in maximum coefficient of lift.

Fig 4.1 comparison of coefficient of lift (C_L) with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 0.3 percent of chord

Fig 4.2 Pressure contour for the modified model with blower at 0.3 percent of chord at $\alpha=5^\circ$

Fig 4.3 Pressure contour for the modified model with blower at 0.3 percent of chord at $\alpha=25^\circ$

The pressure variation induced by the blower was studied by using the pressure contour as shown in fig 4.2 & 4.3. In this case, the effect of blowing is feasible only in higher angle of attacks. Because in lower angle of attacks the free stream velocity gets accelerated before the blowing region is higher than that of blowing velocity. Hence the blowing effect is not influenced at lower angle of attacks as shown in fig 4.2 But in higher angle of attacks the accelerated velocity before the blowing region is lower than the blowing velocity. Hence the flow remains attached in higher angle of attacks by the influence of blowing as shown in fig 4.3

2) *Drag characteristics:* The comparison of drag characteristic of the baseline and modified model with blower at 30 percent of total chord length is studied using graph plot between coefficient of drag vs angle of attack as shown in fig 4.4 and velocity contours as shown in fig 4.5 & 4.6. Where the drag level increases constantly with respect to increase in angle of attack. The fig 4.4 shows comparison of drag coefficient for baseline and the modified model. In modified model the coefficient of drag slightly descended up to 30° angle of attack when compared with the baseline model.

Fig 4.4 comparison of coefficient of drag (CD) with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 0.3 percent of chord

Fig 4.5. Velocity contour for the modified model with blower at 0.3 percent of chord at $\alpha=5^\circ$

Fig 4.6 Velocity contour for the modified model with blower at 0.3 percent of chord at $\alpha=25^\circ$

The velocity variation induced by the blower was studied by using the velocity contour as shown in fig 4.5 & 4.6. The velocity in the upper surface of the airfoil is affected by the blower at 30 percent of total chord length. In lower angle of attack the velocity in the blower area is maintained constantly as the initial portion of the leading-edge as shown in fig 4.5. Hence in higher angle of attacks the blowing velocity helps in reattachment of the flow, because the flow starts to separate on that blowing region as shown in fig 4.6. From fig 4.7, we see that the L/D ratio of the modified model is greater than the baseline model only at higher angle of attack above $\alpha=15^\circ$. Whereas in lower angle of attack the L/D ratio of the modified model is low when compare to the baseline model.

Fig 4.7 comparison of L/D ratio with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 0.3 percent of chord

B. Blowing at 50% Of chord

1) *Lift characteristics:* The comparison of lift characteristic of the baseline and modified model with blower at 50 percent of total chord length is studied using graph plot between coefficient of lift vs angle of attack as shown in fig 4.8 and pressure contours as shown in fig 4.9 & 4.10.

Fig 4.8 comparison of coefficient of lift (CL) with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 0.5 percent of chord

In baseline model the maximum coefficient of lift is 1.1208114 which obtains at 15° AOA. Whereas, in modified model with blower at 50 percent of total chord length attains maximum coefficient of lift at 20° is 1.2054965. In baseline model the stall angle takes place between 15° to 20° . But in the modified model the stall angle takes place between 20° to 25° . The effect of using blower in the modified model is to increase stall angle as well as increase in maximum coefficient of lift.

Fig 4.10 Pressure contour for the modified model with blower at 50 percent of total chord at $\alpha=5^\circ$

Fig 4.11 Pressure contour for the modified model with blower at 50 percent of total chord at $\alpha=20^\circ$

The pressure variation induced by the blower was studied by using the pressure contour as shown in fig 4.10 & 4.11. In this case, the effect of blowing is feasible only in higher angle of attacks. Because in lower angle of attacks the free stream velocity gets accelerated before the blowing region is higher than that of blowing velocity. Hence the blowing effect is not influenced at lower angle of attacks as shown in fig 4.10. But in higher angle of attacks the accelerated velocity before the blowing region is lower than the blowing velocity. Hence the flow remains attached in higher angle of attacks by the influence of blowing as shown in fig 4.11

2) *Drag characteristics*: The comparison of drag characteristic of the baseline and modified model with blower at 50 percent of total chord length is studied using graph plot between coefficient of drag vs angle of attack as shown in fig 4.12 and velocity contours as shown in fig 4.13 & 4.14.

Fig 4.12 comparison of coefficient of drag (CD) with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 0.5 percent of chord

Where the drag level increases constantly with respect to increase in angle of attack. The fig 4.12 shows comparison of drag coefficient for baseline and the modified model. In modified model the coefficient of drag slightly descended up to 15° angle of attack when compared with the baseline model.

Fig 4.13 Velocity contour for the modified model with blower at 0.5 percent of chord at $\alpha=5^\circ$

Fig 4.14 Velocity contour for the modified model with blower at 0.5 percent of chord at $\alpha=20^\circ$

The velocity variation induced by the blower was studied by using the velocity contour as shown in fig 4.13 & 4.14. The velocity in the upper surface of the airfoil is affected by the blower at 50 percent of total chord length. In higher angle of attack the flow starts to separate before the blowing area. Hence the blowing at 0.5 percent chord helps in reattach the flow.

Fig 4.15 comparison of L/D ratio with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 0.5 percent of chord

From fig 4.15, we see that the L/D ratio of the modified model is greater than the baseline model only at higher angle of attack above $\alpha=15^\circ$. Whereas in lower angle of attack the L/D ratio of the modified model is low when compare to the baseline model.

C. Blowing at 80% of chord

1) Lift characteristics: The comparison of lift characteristic of the baseline and modified model with blower at 80 percent of total chord length is studied using graph plot between coefficient of lift vs angle of attack as shown in fig 5.17 and pressure contours as shown in fig 5.18.

Fig 4.16 comparison of coefficient of lift (CL) with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 80 percent of chord

In baseline model the maximum coefficient of lift is 1.1208114 which obtains at 15° AOA. Whereas, in modified model with blower at 80 percent of total chord length attains maximum coefficient of lift at 20° is 1.1456972. In baseline model the stall angle takes place between 15° to 20° . But in the modified model the stall angle takes place between 20° to 25° . The effect of using blower in the modified model is to increase stall angle as well as increase in maximum coefficient of lift.

Fig 4.17 Pressure contour for the modified model with blower at 0.8 percent of chord at $\alpha=5^\circ$

Fig 4.18 Pressure contour for the modified model with blower at 0.8 percent of chord at $\alpha=20^\circ$

The pressure variation induced by the blower was studied by using the pressure contour as shown in fig 5.18. In this case, the effect of blowing is feasible only in lower angle of attacks. Because in lower angle of attacks the free stream velocity gets accelerated before the blowing region is higher than that of blowing velocity. Hence the blowing effect is not influenced at lower angle of attacks as shown in fig 5.18.a. But in higher angle of attacks the accelerated velocity before the blowing region is lower than the blowing velocity. Hence the flow remains attached in higher angle of attacks by the influence of blowing as shown in fig 5.18.b.

2) *Drag characteristics:* The comparison of drag characteristic of the baseline and modified model with blower at 80 percent of total chord length is studied using graph plot between coefficient of drag vs angle of attack as shown in fig 4.19 and velocity contours as shown in fig 4.20 & 4.21.

Fig 4.19 comparison of coefficient of drag (CD) with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 80percent of chord

Where the drag level increases constantly with respect to increase in angle of attack. The fig 4.19 shows comparison of drag coefficient for baseline and the modified model. In modified model the coefficient of drag slightly descended up to 15° angle of attack when compared with the baseline model.

Fig 4.20 Velocity contour for the modified model with blower at 0.8 percent of chord at $\alpha=5^\circ$

Fig 4.21 Velocity contour for the modified model with blower at 0.8 percent of chord at $\alpha=20^\circ$

The velocity variation induced by the blower was studied by using the velocity contour as shown in fig 4.20 & 4.21. The velocity in the upper surface of the airfoil is affected by the blower at 80 percent of the total chord length. In higher angle of attack the flow starts to separate before the blowing area. Hence the blowing at 80 percent of the chord helps in reattach the flow.

Fig 4.22 comparison of L/D ratio with respect to various angles of attack (α) of baseline and modified model with blower at 0.8 percent of chord

From fig 4.22, we see that the L/D ratio of the modified model with blowing at 80% of chord is not much effective in any angle of attack. In spite of, increasing lift in higher angle of attacks but the drag is also increase. This is the reason for decrease in L/D ratio.

D. DISCUSSION

From the results obtained and analysed the optimum design is selected by comparing the results such that a higher lift while lower drag is produced. At 0° angle of attack, L/D RATIO is maximum in modified model with blower at 30 percent of chord. Because, in 0° angle of attack the flow in upper region remains attached in larger area and starts to separate nearer to the trailing edge. So, the blowing is effective only at 30 percent of chord. But, when the angle of attack increases the flow gets separated formerly with respect to the angle of attack. So, the blowing is effective only at 30 percent of chord.

In overall view, the most effective design of the wing is to fix the wing at 5° angle of attack and place the blower at 30 percent of chord.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, the effect of blowing location has been studied on a modified NACA 2415 airfoil with blowing. Blowing velocity was done for various locations such as 0.3c, 0.5c and 0.8c at various angle of attack ranging from 0 to 35 in increments of 5. Based on the above study, the following conclusions are made.

1. The optimised blowing location is found as 30% of the chord on the wing. Beyond 0.3c, the influence of blowing is less significant.
3. The wings leading edge with blowing shows the improvement in the aerodynamic characteristics is due to the addition of momentum through blowing jet, which in turn delays the flow separation by energising the flow.
4. Even at higher angle of attacks, the flow on the downstream of the wing is still attached as the result of blowing.
5. The modified model with blowing also results in increasing the stall angle. The stall angle of baseline model is 15° which were increased up to 25° in the modified model with blower at 30% of chord and 20° in the modified model with blower at 50% and 80% of the chord.

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